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Introduction

Long-range search is essential for nearly all aspects of animal behaviour from locating mates and food to population dispersal^{6,7,8,9,10}. Deciphering search behaviour is important for understanding sensorimotor translation in the nervous system and its role in an organism's survival. Translating the search process is useful for generating efficient algorithms for artificial intelligence, robotics, and internet search protocols, among others^{11,12}. Search involves the discrimination of environmental cues, identification of relevant objects, and the subsequent active translation of the organism

toward a particular resource or location^{6,8}. These conditions demand a continuous and dynamic assessment of stimulus space with subsequent action to accurately locate distant targets. As a consequence, understanding proximate mechanisms of search behaviour requires not only the evaluation of initial and final conditions of the search but also the quantitative measurement of stimulus context and behavioural response at all points of the search trajectory^{8,10}.

Flying insects play an integral role in human and environmental ecosystems as pests, vectors, pollinators, and nutrient cyclers. While it is obvious that each of these scenarios requires insects to find objects of interest, it is unclear what features of the natural world are utilized for this purpose. Here, I define long-range behaviour^{6,8,9} as locating objects at distances extending three orders of magnitude of body size (e.g., >10 m for a 1-cm-long insect). At these scales, most insects cannot visually resolve many cues of interest such as fruits, flowers, leaves, or conspecifics, thus necessitating multimodal integration to localize the object of interest. Therefore, insects have been suggested to employ long-range optomotor anemotaxis (see Table A.1 on page 89 for a glossary of keywords) in flight by integrating wide-field visual cues, wind direction for upwind orientation, and olfactory cues from the fine-scale structure of odour plumes^{8,13,14}. Insects are known to utilize wide-field cues such as horizon, slip, ground translation, and sky rotation to maintain stable flight^{8,15,16,17,18}. Insects have been shown to make use of small-field cues such as perspective and motion parallax to localize objects while walking^{19,20} and measure distance travelled in flight^{21,22}. However, we do not know if insects make use of these features to rapidly discriminate, localize, and navigate to objects amidst a complex three-dimensional (3D) landscape while in flight. For example, while difficult to achieve in stochastic real-world environments, it is possible that insects could utilize a form of image matching²³ to the two-dimensional (2D) pattern and odour identity of relevant objects during long-range search without employing 3D or odour plume features.

Deconstructing multimodal search behaviour, therefore, necessitates the precise measurement of a flying insect's response to objects under relevant ecological contexts that provide dynamic 3D

visual scenery, windscapes, and odour flux over large spatial and temporal scales. The detection and response of flying insects to objects and multimodal cues in the natural world have been well-studied in pollinator systems, albeit at relatively short spatial scales (<2 m)^{24,25,26}. However, due to their small size, relatively high flight speeds, and large dispersal scales, a quantification of where and when flying insects detect and respond to objects at larger scales required for long-range behaviour is relatively unknown^{8,10}. Essentially, we can either track the insect or the stimulus in nature, but not both simultaneously. For these reasons, such observations have been limited to confined areas (~ 10 m²)²⁷ and nonecological^{15,28,29} or unimodal^{30,31} conditions that cannot replicate the search process in its entirety. Virtual reality (VR) technology provides an opportunity to precisely control stimulus delivery and modulates behavioural output. By using minimal stimulus features such as moving stripes, spots, and binary odour pulses, VR arenas have allowed us to understand sensorimotor coupling and integration mechanisms in the nervous system^{15,28,29,30,31,32}. However, these arenas cannot be used to assess long-range search behaviour, nor have they been applied to ecological questions to date^{15,28,29,30,31,32}. For example, vertical bars, a commonly used 2D stimulus in most VRs, cannot be utilized to assess depth cues such as perspective and motion parallax^{16,28,32,33,34,35,36}. Existing arenas also lack the capability to simultaneously present dynamic visual scenery containing 3D objects in the presence of airflow fields and odour flux^{15,28,29,30,31,32} at large scales critical for the multimodal search behaviour exhibited by flying insects in nature^{8,13,23,37}.

In this dissertation, I focus on deconstructing the search behaviour of flying insects using virtual reality. I first establish a need for Virtual Reality arenas for insect research. I then discuss their history and how advances in technology enabled us to have a nuanced understanding of behaviour. Using such VR arenas, multiple researchers from all over the world have deciphered numerous behaviours and their neural underpinnings, down to the circuitry of individual neurons. I also remark on how knowledge of such detailed, mechanistic understandings have pushed the boundaries of autonomous navigation in robots and will continue to do so.

We then discuss how the current VR approaches were unsatisfactory for our goals. Therefore, I set out to build an arena that was capable of providing naturalistic visual, olfactory and mechanical input to a wide range of flying insects. As this was a tall order and previously untested on our choice of model organisms, I had to start from the basics. This began with ensuring elementary requirements such as making our flies fly on tethers, respond to visual stimuli from monitors, utilize olfactory and airflow cues in closed loop. This established a proof of concept pilot VR arena that can provide multimodal input in closed loop.

However, the pilot VR lacked in many aspects, such as slow refresh rate monitors, limited field of view of stimuli, bulky microscope for closed loop, primitive graphics etc. To address these critical shortcomings, I built a state of the art VR arena with high refresh rate gaming monitors, 360° visual, olfactory and airflow stimuli, compact closed loop setup and naturalistic graphics. I then verified the functioning of the VR on our flies using a well characterized behaviour like optomotor response. As I intended to give naturalistic stimuli, I had to characterize other critical parameters such as gain as they play a big role in the dynamics of behaviour.

Using the VR, I then established foreground object segmentation amidst complex background using diverse species of flies playing different roles in ecosystem. I showed the role of size and distance in target localization and the use of motion parallax. I then showed usage of airflow cues in the absence of visual cues which has implications in high flying and nocturnal migrating insects. Finally, I decoupled sensory integration of vision, wind and odour in plume following behaviour.

Finally, I show the future of VR and the diverse possibilities using “Virtual Surreality” experiments to deconstruct features that are very hard to do in real life. And how VR, along with study of diverse species in the natural habitat would push the boundaries of our understanding.

0.1 CHAPTER SUMMARY

In **chapter 1** on page 7, I discuss the need for VR arenas to deconstruct insect behaviour. The insights gained will not only improve our understanding on animal brains, but also aid in advancement of bio-inspired robots.

Chapter 2 on page 19 is a first person account, catering to the obstacles one would encounter and key factors that should be considered before developing the a virtual reality arena, detailing the issues that can potentially derail a new VR project.

Chapter 3 on page 39 explores the dynamic landscapes, windscares and odourscares that were created to approximate stimuli that an insect might encounter in the natural world. It delves deeper into the tests employed for the VR validation.

Chapter 4 on page 63 assessed the critical parameters of long-range search including reactive distance, perspective, motion parallax, anemotaxis, and plume following using our multimodal virtual reality (MultiMoVR) arena.

Chapter 5 on page 82 discusses how my results open avenues of exploration for a variety of biological and technological applications.

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Using virtual worlds to understand insect navigation for bio-inspired systems

Autonomous navigation by artificial systems in complex natural environments has been a major challenge of robotics. In real-world conditions, sensory input is spatiotemporally complex, multimodal, has large dynamic ranges, and fluctuates stochastically, making precise predictions virtually impossible for current technologies. However, 500 million years of evolutionary adaptations

have allowed insects to accomplish this task with less than half a million neurons. Insects perform a wide array of complex behaviours over large spatial and temporal scales from rapid aerial manoeuvres^{38,39}, long-distance plume following^{13,9}, and intercontinental multigenerational migrations^{40,41,42}. Insects execute these computationally intensive processes^{13,43,33,7,44,45} despite their limited computational resources, while our robot counterparts with ample resources struggle in the real world^{46,12,47,48,49,50}. A mechanistic understanding of how insects parse complex natural environments has direct implications on how brains integrate multimodal information and can inspire bio-based solutions for autonomous robots and smarter computer algorithms that can parse multiple inputs and respond appropriately in the real world^{46,12,47,48,49,50,51}. Dissection of insect behaviour demands precise quantification of where and when insects detect and respond to objects in ethological contexts, while simultaneously being able to dynamically manipulate these stimuli to deduce causal relationships. However, this is a challenging endeavour due to insects' small size, high speeds, and the large spatio-temporal scales in which they navigate. Field studies have limited manipulative power, and lab assays are constrained to small scales in simplified environments. Virtual Reality (VR) arenas overcome many of these challenges by restraining the animal and artificially providing sensory stimuli that can be updated based on the animal's actions^{28,52}. Present-day VRs incorporate multiple modalities^{53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,19} natural scene complexity¹, and can simultaneously record from the brain²⁹, or present virtual stimuli while the animal is freely flying^{30,17}. This enables fine-scale manipulation of stimulus and response dynamics to assess brain and behaviour^{44,28}. Here, I acknowledge these technological developments and discuss the potential to apply insect VR research to bio-inspired robots. To achieve this potential, I advocate the need for transdisciplinary approaches that integrate neuroscience, engineering, ecology and natural history to properly translate insect behaviour to artificial systems.

1.1 WHY STUDY INSECTS?

Insects forage, disperse, and find mates and other objects in the noisy natural environment over distances that are many orders larger than their body size^{9,40,1,8}. Insect vision is fundamental for navigation, stable flight control, object avoidance and target tracking^{46,61,62}. However, vision alone is insufficient for such long-range target searches due to their limited spatial acuity^{9,8,61}. They overcome this limitation with long-range odour plume following and multimodal sensory integration during search^{7,54,57,1,34}. Mosquitoes, for example, locate humans by integrating the olfactory, visual, and heat signatures of their warm-blooded hosts^{57,63}. Nevertheless, plume following is a challenging task since advection and turbulence in air chaotically disperse the plume into a meandering, intermittent stream of packets^{13,7}. Wind not only affects how insects follow plumes, but also the magnitude and direction of their migrations^{40,41,42,64}. Sound and vibration also play an important role in locating objects from a distance for several insects^{43,55,65,66}. Performing these diverse tasks necessitates that insects parse the natural world's complex features amidst a noisy background. These features are spread over multiple sensory systems, from hyperspectral visual signals, polarization patterns, stochastic olfactory input, turbulent airflows, near and far-field sounds, and the Earth's magnetic field, among others. (Figure 1.1 on page 10)

Insect brains receive sensory input from the environment and rapidly perform multiscale feature extraction to detect edges, shapes, odor identity, wind speed, and other aspects. Using these features, they estimate self motion, figure ground discrimination, track targets, detect obstacles, localize sound, etc.^{55,1,67,68,69,70,71}. Along with these features, insects must store diverse internal states that encode goal-oriented behaviours, mating status, hunger levels, and other physiological conditions. They must then integrate these multiple sensory modalities while accounting for their internal states, position, and orientation of self with respect to the outside world and output motor commands.^{44,53,54,57,58,63,72,73,74}

Figure 1.1: Insects make use of a wide variety of cues available in nature over large spatial and temporal scales to perform diverse behaviours. They use landmarks, horizon, sky polarization, and magnetic fields for orientation, dispersal, and migration. Using wide-field visual cues, wind, and odor plumes, they approach distant visual targets. By adding ultraviolet, electric fields, humidity, and temperature cues, they make short-range decisions for landing.

If we want our robots to be truly autonomous in our worlds, they too must perform many of these tasks and computations. The challenges currently facing our artificial systems arise due to the structural complexity of real-world scenes, unmapped environments, unpredictability of turbulence, noisy sensors, limited online computational power, range anxiety, and other technological limitations. For example, despite our current computational capabilities, foreground segmentation, monocular depth sensing, and object localization in real environments is still an open problem in computer vision¹². GPS denied navigation with only onboard computation in uncharted territories is a challenge⁷⁵. Turbulence in open environments and rotorwash makes plume following difficult for robots^{49,50}. Insects measure the same sensory quantities, face analogous algorithmic challenges, and have to perform similar tasks with limited resources⁴⁶. We can take inspiration from the neuronal anatomy, stereotyped behaviours, and underlying computational algorithms of insect navigation to enhance our artificial systems and allow them to navigate in stochastic real-world environments.

1.2 VIRTUAL REALITY FOR INSECT RESEARCH

The general premise of virtual reality is to hold an organism in place and artificially modify its sensory environment. This is a precise modification, as one has to measure a relevant behavioural output of the organism, interpret what those actions might do to its sensory input in the natural world and quickly modify the artificial stimuli. The output measured could be the tail beat of fishes, limbs of a rodent, head orientation of a human or the flapping wing of an insect etc.

Insect VRs have been around for more than half a century and were originally created to examine insect flight and visual systems, particularly optomotor reflexes (Figure 1.2 on page 12). For comprehensive historical overviews, see reviews^{28,61,62}. Here I concentrate on recent advances, with acknowledgment of the extensive history behind these techniques. Due to technological constraints in sensors, computation, and displays, initial VRs were built by surrounding tethered flies with rotating drums^{76,77,78} (see Table 1.1 on page 15 for a list of recent advances in VR arenas). The drums were lined with mathematically simple visual patterns such as bars, gratings, dots, and others that provided optic flow. With technological advances, these patterns were animated using cathode-ray monitors and custom LED panels to provide different kinds of optic flow^{59,71,79,80,81}.

Recent advances in gaming displays and 3D projection technologies provide high refresh rate visual input that allow the use of colour¹, complex 3D patterns^{30,82,83}, polarization cues^{84,16}, hyperspectral, and naturalistic scenes¹ while simultaneously recording neural signals from the brain²⁹ and optogenetically manipulating them^{85,82,86,84}. In the recent past, scientists have elucidated the neural basis of many behaviours, such as how insects detect motion⁶², control their walking speed⁸⁷, perform spontaneous turns^{53,62,88}, track bars^{89,67,59}, avoid obstacles^{59,62} and navigate to virtual 2D^{1,82,83}, 3D^{1,82,83} and naturalistic objects^{1,82,83}. VR has also helped reveal the role of the insect central complex in navigation^{44,90}. Using VR, scientists have discovered that central complex performs diverse computations ranging from integration of angular headings and velocities^{72,91}, in-

Abb. 1. Fixiert fliegende Biene in der Versuchsanordnung

Figure 1.2: Peter Kunze and colleagues built one of the first Virtual Reality arenas for insects. Adapted from⁷⁶

ternal goal guided navigation⁷⁴, proprioceptive cues from halteres⁹², integrating polarization cues to encode sun position during menotaxis^{16,93,94}, and can represent heading even after arbitrary scene remapping^{73,95}. With advances in 3D printing, VRs are now capable of providing precise directional airflow (not wind per se) even in closed-loop¹. Using VR, flies are shown to use bilateral differences in arista to measure wind speed and direction⁹⁶. In VR, flies also integrate wind and visual cues as a sum of spatiotemporally filtered signals⁵³ with selective attention⁹⁷. Flies can also navigate in virtual worlds using only wind speed and direction in the absence of any optic flow, an ability critical for high flying night migrants^{41,1}. Technological enhancements, particularly faster valves^{98,99} and newer tethering paradigms^{100,101,102} enable the use of olfaction in VR arenas. Flies in olfactory VR have been shown to use concentration differences across their antennae to orient toward higher concentrations¹⁰¹. They also follow wind tunnel-like virtual plumes in VR by integrating visual, wind, and odor cues¹. In *Drosophila*, attractive odors reverse the valence of visual objects⁵⁸. Using recent advances in mosquito genetics, thermotaxis was shown to be enhanced by visual landing cues and exposure to CO₂⁵⁷. CO₂ exposure also modulated vision but not vice versa⁶³. Honeybees can also learn using cues from VR^{83,103,104}. Using stereo speakers in VR, flies were shown to localize sound using differences in inter-antennal vibrations⁵⁵. Complexity in insects' 3D sound localization strategies limits our inferential reach using stereo speakers⁴³. Using a 360° speaker array and a panoramic visual input, crickets have been shown to use virtual sound and visual input for decision making and source localization⁵⁶. Finally, migrating moths have been found to use the Earth's magnetic field and visual landmarks to steer flight in VR¹⁰⁵.

The VRs presented until now have used tethered insects due to convenience and technological barriers in performing neurophysiological recordings as they fly around freely. To estimate the amount of intended motion of the insect, different methods such as floating balls^{82,106,107}, torque compensators^{61,76}, masked photodiodes^{61,108}, and camera tracking^{16,109} are used, all of which excel at estimating the yaw torque. However, flying insects also simultaneously thrust, pitch, and roll dur-

ing banking turns and evasive maneuvers, enabling 3D flight^{38,39}. We still lack the ability to measure the subtle changes in wing kinematics in real-time for closed-loop 3D VR flight. Tethering also can restrict maneuverability, particularly in Dipterans. Flies use mechanosensory cues from halteres, which act like gyroscopes to estimate self-motion¹¹⁰. Halteres are also suggested to provide timing information for wing beats⁶⁰. However, these cues are hampered by tethering⁶², making tethered flight an inaccurate model of free flight. This doesn't appear to affect higher-level behaviours such as decision making, as the insect choices observed are not measurably different between VR and nature in the cases tested^{1,82}. However, tethering artifacts pose challenges for studying the biomechanics of insect flight in VR as sensory conflicts can cause erroneous behaviours³⁰. With the advent of newer tether designs that can freely yaw, partial aspects of free flight have been recovered¹⁰². Recently, using real-time 3D tracking and rapid computation, freely flying insects were provided with closed-loop visual feedback^{15,17,30}. What this VR lost in manipulative abilities of imaging and neural recording, it gained by simulating genuine free flight in VR.

1.3 KNOWLEDGE GAPS

Insect brains have evolved to convert the noisy, complex, multimodal sensory input of the natural world into intricate movement patterns to perform various behaviours¹¹³. As neuroethologists with a long term goal to understand the organism and its brain, it is prudent to also study the organism using ecologically relevant stimuli^{113,114,115,116,85,13,33,7}. This is a good strategy not only due to physiological constraints imposed by the organisms' evolutionary history but also due to the physics of the natural world. For example, visual systems are tuned to the statistics of natural worlds and behave robustly over a wide range of input parameters, such as contrast, spatial frequency, and spatiotemporal correlations^{115,116,85}. However, natural visual stimuli differ from artificial, "simple" stimuli¹¹⁵ and are sensitive to even slight changes in input parameters. Simple stimuli such as

Table 1.1: Recent advances in virtual reality technologies developed for studying insects

Modality	Advance	Description	Ref
Visual	2D patterns	2D optic flow stimuli with bars, gratings using drums, motors and custom LED panels	61,62,79 80,81,76
	3D objects	3D optic flow stimuli with spots, cones, and spheres using displays and projectors	111,82,86,84
	Naturalistic scenes	3D colour scenery with naturalistic stimuli using gaming technology	1
	Ultra Violet	Multispectrum display with arbitrary visual and UV wavelengths	112
	Polarization	Polarized visual input with tunable angle of polarization	84,16
Olfactory	Odor	A freely rotating magnetic tether with odor input.	100,101
	360° Odor	A 360° closed-loop odor delivery with arbitrary odorscapes	1
Mechanosensory	Wind	Laminar airflow delivery with arbitrary direction	53,54,97
	360° Wind	A 360° closed-loop wind delivery with arbitrary windscares	1
	Free flight	A closed-loop arena for freely flying insects	15,30
	Sound	A 360° sound speaker array with arbitrary soundscapes	55,56
Magnetosensory	Compass	Magnetic field input with tunable field direction	105

bars and stripes, which are mathematically well defined, have been crucial to my characterization of insect visual systems^{59,61,62,67,69,71,117}. Nevertheless, their geometry is fundamentally incapable of providing complex perspective and parallax cues that surround us in the real world¹. The use of naturalistic stimuli had been limited due to technological constraints. With the advent of faster display technologies, we should use this opportunity to devise new ways of systematically quantifying ethologically relevant stimuli¹¹⁸ and use them in our VRs.

Polarization and UV cues in the sky also provide complex spatiotemporal cues for insects during navigation^{54,16,93,94}. These cues are particularly hard to study due to the limits of my own eyes and limited commercial equipment to measure them. Devising techniques to incorporate these cues into our VRs would let us see our organisms in a new light, both literally and conceptually^{84,112}.

Similarly, the air surrounding us is almost always turbulent, stochastically tossing around odours. Insects have evolved to track plumes of odourant mixtures in turbulent environments and behave more robustly than in laminar environments^{13,114,119}. Our inability to precisely measure, model, simulate and simulate turbulent wind and odour plumes have required us to study insect behaviour in the laminar airflow used in most wind tunnels⁷. This has restricted our understanding of the mechanistic basis of olfactory processing in insects. By using turbulent wind tunnels, faster odour delivery systems^{98,99}, high-resolution odour data¹²⁰, and computational power, we can understand plume tracking behaviour in complex and turbulent environments⁷.

Despite the many shortcomings of the tethered paradigm, it does provide precise multimodal sensory stimulation and enables unfettered access to the brain for neuronal recording and imaging. To close the loop, appendage movements are often transformed into yaw velocities, limiting the virtual flight to a 2D plane. But flies perform manoeuvres in 3D by rapidly changing wing stroke dynamics³⁸. By themselves, these are challenging measurements to perform. A system that can measure these parameters in real-time is a daunting task. Another approach in progress is the use of two-axis torque meters that can simultaneously measure yaw and thrust¹²¹. With advances in deep

learning for tracking and pose estimation, micro-electromechanical system 3D torque sensors, GHz radar we may soon be able to measure these flight parameters on the fly and close the loop in 3D.

The marriage of natural history and VR technology using diverse organisms will advance the field of neuroethology for years to come.

1.4 THE ROAD AHEAD

In the process of understanding insect vision, multiple algorithms^{122,46,47,48,49,50,51} have been implemented in robots. By studying insects in more complex environments, we can understand how they parse the complex visual input stream with limited resources. The mechanisms underlying their ability to perform foreground segmentation from an uncalibrated moving camera, sense depth using monocular motion parallax cues, and localize occluded objects amidst clutter would undoubtedly uncover a plethora of mechanisms useful to artificial systems. These mechanisms directly translate into better bio-inspired computer vision algorithms and robust real-world navigation of autonomous robots.

The lack of portable, rapid, and sensitive volatile sensors has been a major barrier to devising autonomous olfactory robots. Robots that mimic insect plume following strategies based on laminar airflow wind tunnel studies perform well only in tunnel environments^{49,50}. Understanding insect plume following in turbulent conditions would generate novel algorithms for bio-inspired autonomous robots that operate in the real world. This would enable robots to be used for disaster management, search and rescue, tracking pollutants and hazardous waste, and many other applications. Understanding how insects combine multiple ambiguous and noisy streams to perform precisely targeted behaviours would also help us devise better decision making algorithms for robust autonomous performance. By unraveling flight algorithms in 3D by including pitch, yaw, and roll, we can also improve our bio-inspired algorithms currently limited to 2D. With enhanced multisen-

sory parsing and integration of natural scenes, we can truly navigate a flying drone autonomously in 3D.

Insects perform a wide variety of complex cognitive tasks in nature, such as predation, parasitic behaviour, migration, swarming, mimicry, social learning and memory, nest building, diapause, and others. However, the majority of VR studies on insects have so far focused on understanding reflexes and sensory systems that necessitate the use of simple stimuli rather than more ecologically complex inputs. This problem is exacerbated by the knowledge gaps in our organism's ecology and natural history. We need to know the natural history of the species, how it forages, disperses, and mates¹²². We also must uncover the sensory stimuli that elicit such responses, as no VR study can supplant the fundamental necessity of studying insects in their natural habitat. In the absence of such crucial data, we are forced to provide abstract or ecologically irrelevant stimuli to investigate their behaviour. Moreover, to address the diverse questions and behaviours that are commonplace in insects, there is a pressing need to diversify our model systems beyond *Drosophila*^{123,122}. Using comparative approaches, we must study an array of emerging model organisms, performing a variety of complex behaviours in their respective natural habitats^{123,40,7,45,1} while simultaneously recording and imaging their brains. This will help in uncovering the proximate and ultimate basis of brain and behaviour and extract general principles for common challenging problems. These approaches will not only enhance our understanding of the brain but also help us design bio-inspired autonomous robots and smarter computer algorithms.